

Stanford University CS229 course notes

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Lecture1:

- The course is about machine learning.
- The course will look into:
 - Supervised learning
 - Regression: such as prediction
 - Classification
 - Unsupervised learning
 - Anomaly detection
 - Clustering
 - Dimensionality reduction
 - Deep learning (representation learning): it could be supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement.
 - Learning theory: is the basics of how is learning happen, and different ways of learning.
 - Reinforcement learning:
- Linear algebra:
 - Vectors: which can be put as a single row or a single column.
 - Matrix:
 - MxN means a matrix with M rows, N columns.
 - Identity matrix: is a matrix with all zeros and the diagonal is all ones
 - Diagonal matrix: is a matrix with all zeros except where the $M = N$ are non-zero numbers.
 - Symmetric matrix: is a matrix that has the same elements on the two sides of the diagonal.
 - Transpose of the matrix: $A_{ij} = \text{transpose } A_{ji}$
 - The trace is $\sum_i A_{ij}$.
 - Vector-vector operations: inner product / dot product. Which are distinct but, in this course, they will be the same. $X^T Y$
 - Outer product: $Y^T X$
 - You can think of the rank of the matrix as if one matrix is a sheet of paper and you are adding more sheets (matrices) on top of it.
 - Matrix vector: you can use the inner product to multiply a matrix by a vector and you will get a vector $A(M \times N) \cdot X(N) = AX(M)$
 - Matrix-Matrix operations: $(M \times K) \cdot (K \times N) = (M \times N)$
- Why linear algebra in machine learning?
 - To represent data.
 - Covariance matrices
 - Calculus: such as
 - Gradients
 - Hessians

- Jacobians
 - Kernel method

- Geometrical interpretation:
 - A matrix that maps all the vectors in the input space to the vectors in the output space is a “**full rank matrix**” and that is on a three-dimensional cartesian space.
 - When there is a full rank matrix then there is an inverse matrix that maps the output vectors to the input vectors
 - **Rank deficient:** is a matrix that is not a full rank, and that such as rank-2 then the matrix will map the point on (subspace) two dimensions in the three-dimensional space, in both the input and the output. And in case there is a point out of the sub space then the vector to the point gets decomposed into two vectors and calculated using Pythagoras triangle rule
- ★ Since the projection of a point is always the closest point on a subspace to it then the line between them is always orthogonal.
 - Projection matrix: projection matrix $(V) = \begin{bmatrix} VV^T \\ V^TV \end{bmatrix} b = V (V^TV)^{-1}V^T b$
- Now in a cartesian space you take the unite sphere and run it through a full rank matrix as an input, the output shape will look like an ellipsoid, and all the input point will have a change in length and direction but, only few vectors such as 3 in 3x3 matrix will have change in magnitude without change in direction, these are eigen vectors and the eigen value is the ratio between the input and the output vector of the eigen vector.
- And with that said: the rank of the matrix refers to the non-zero eigen values

Lecture2

- Determinant = the product of all eigen values
- Volume (output shape) / volume (input shape)

- Determinant is important when calculating PDF and linear operations.
- Spectrum: collection of eigen values.
- Spectral theorem: all symmetric and square matrices have real eigen values and orthogonal eigen vectors. Ex: Hessians, covariance matrices, kernel.
- Quadratic forms: for square matrix (A) and a vector (x), $(x^T A x)$ is the quadratic form.

$$x^T Bx = x^T Ax \text{ -----} \rightarrow B = \frac{1}{2}A + \frac{1}{2}A^T$$

- Definitiveness: when the quadratic form of (A) bigger than zero for all (x) does not equal zero, then (A) is positive definite.
- And when (A) is less than zero (A) is negative definite, and when (A) is bigger or equal to zero, smaller or equal to zero, then (A) is positive semi definite and negative semi definite respectively.
- And when (A) is neither bigger nor smaller than zero then it is indefinite

- When the angle between (a) and (b) is smaller, equal, bigger than 90° then the value of $(a^T b)$ is bigger, equal, smaller than zero respectively

- Decomposition:
 - o Singular value decomposition
 - o Eigen value decomposition
 - o Cholesky decomposition

operation	A	Decom	In the next table
SVD	any	$A = USV^T$	$A(x) = U(S(V^T(x)))$
EVD	square	$A = UDU^{-1}$	$A(x) = U(D(U^{-1}(x)))$

- where U and V are orthogonal matrices, and S and D are diagonal

A	Step1	Step2	Step3
SVD	V^T rotation	Scaling along axes	U rotation
EVD	U^{-1} rotation	Scaling axes	U inversion

- Matrix calculus:
 - The first derivative of the loss function is gradient and the second derivative is hessian
 - The first derivative of a neural network layer is Jacobian and the second derivative is higher order tensor
 - Gradient $(f(x))$ equals a vector consists of partial derivatives of the function with respect to the variables in the function
 - When (x) is a square matrix in the point above it results in a matrix of partial derivatives.
 - When taking the hessian of (x) we take the second derivative of each element instead of first derivative like above with the gradient.

- The product rule:

- $\nabla_x x^T Ax = \nabla_x x^T Ax + \nabla_x x^T Ax$
 - $= Ax + A^T x$
 - $= x(A + A^T)$
 - $= 2xA$
- The product rule of the derivative is the first term by the derivative of the second added to the derivative of the first term by the second term.
 - Another term is $\nabla_A \log|A| = A^{-1}$ and that is because the derivative of $\log(x)=x^{-1}$
 - Probability review

Lecture3

- CDF: the probability assigned to a set of outcomes that map the values less than or equal to a threshold.
- PDF: it's for continuous probability and the value of the probability is the area under the curve of the distribution.
- With discrete RV we use sum while in continuous use integral.
- The mean and variance of the probability distribution.
- Distributions like: Bernoulli, binomial, gaussian, exponential, geometric, Poisson, uniform.
- And there could be two random variables, like bivariate PMF or PDF
- Bayes theorem: you can decompose the joint into the marginal and the conditional.
- Mean and covariance of the multi variable gaussian
- When looking on a $\{2 \times 2\}$ matrix the covariance is the two elements other than the diagonal.
- Expectation
- Bayes rule still applies even if there is a condition (third variable) in all the terms.
- Statistics is going from data(observations) to parameters, while probability is the opposite

Means parameters to data.

- Training data ---->ML ----->model ----->future data
- MLE
- Likelihood function,
- Independent identical distributed (iid) where the likelihood of all the elements equals the multiplication of all the elements,
- Probability and likelihood are different, the likelihood does not sum to one and the probability is the area under the curve